

Classical Average Energy Conservation in Quantum Bound State Part II

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We argue that there seems to exist a dichotomy in quantum mechanics associated with classically sharp x and t points versus uncertainty in time and position. The quantum free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ is not only associated with spatial resolution due to the wavelength \hbar/p , but with classical values p momentum and $pp/2m$, nonrelativistic kinetic energy We we suggest that these latter are associated with average $\exp(ipx)$ values: $p = p$ $(-i\hbar/dx)\exp(ipx)/\exp(ipx)$ and $pp/2m = -1/2m d/dx d/dx \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx)$. In other words, the sharp value of p is associated with an average value using resolution probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ and so one may create sharp classical x points and time points using averages. The quantum free particle formalism contains both and is further linked with $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)=1$ which shows constant density in space.

In particular, energy conservation uses a sharp $\langle 1/2m pp \rangle$ value at each x as well as $V(x)$, so we suggest these sharp spatial points are associated with averages. As a result, one may create an average of $\exp(ipx)$ s, i.e. $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$, which is quantum in that it represents crests/troughs. This is linked with the average $V(x)=\text{sum over } k \text{ } V_k \exp(ikx)$. In the case of $W(x)$, it is $-1/2m d/dx d/dx W / W = KE_{ave}(x)$ which is linked with the classical $v_{rms}(x)$, but $V(x)$ itself is an average and also linked with classical notions of points in x . Thus, for an infinite bound well, one may have an infinite potential at $x=0$ and $x=L$, sharp x points even though $\exp(ipx)$ is a dynamic quantity with spatial resolution. In other words the classical notion of sharp x and t points arises from quantum averages, but actually even quantum free particles, which contain a sharp p value, have the notion of this classical average built-in. In other words, one starts a priori with a sharp p value, but needs to take an average $-i\hbar/dx \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx)$ in order to obtain a sense of x and t as sharp points. In particular, p average is p at each x and t point, so $p=mv = mx/t$. Thus, we argue for a dichotomy.

Sharp x Versus $\exp(ipx)$ x Resolution Dichotomy

There seems to be a dichotomy in quantum mechanics. On the one hand, uncertainty in time and position for a quantum free particle is expressed by $\exp(-i pp/2m t)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ (nonrelativistically). The spatial part $\exp(ipx)$ is associated with a set of experiments i.e. n -slit interference, where an n -slit apparatus is a classical object. This means that even though the particle has spatial resolution $\exp(ipx)$ (i.e. is not an x point) and the slit apparatus is apparently made of particles which in turn should have spatial resolution and not be sharp, these are second order corrections. The slits are separated by a classically sharp distance which should be of the order of \hbar/p so that p , represented by spatial uncertainty, has probability to interact with both, thus creating an OR probability situation with the dynamic $\exp(ipx)$ probability. In an interference experiment, one argues that the particle in question cannot be a point, but the slits can have sharp edges (associated with points). As a result, we argue for a dichotomy in quantum mechanics. This seems to exist already at the $\exp(ipx)$ level because one has a sharp p value (momentum), but a resolution (or uncertainty in space) in two dimensions. These two

dimensions are associated with a constant modulus, i.e. there is an imposed classical constraint. This classical constraint suggests that each x point has equal weight. This, however, is an average calculation based on $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$ representing a kind of average density. The sharp value of p may be written as $-i\hbar/dx \exp(ipx)/\exp(ipx)$ and the sharp value of $pp/2m$ as $-1/2m \hbar^2/dx^2 \exp(ipx)/\exp(ipx)$. Thus, p and $pp/2m$ which are classical sharp values are also average values for the quantum resolution probability $\exp(ipx)$. They are associated with the sharp classical x points, linked with $p=mx/t$ and with the experiment of striking a target at each x . The notion of a sharp p for a quantum free particle is immediately associated with $p=mx/t$, suggesting sharp x, t values (which are averages), but at the same time with resolutions $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$. The latter is experimentally seen in an n -slit experiment.

In other words, there is a dichotomy of sharp classical values as well as resolutions in quantum mechanics. This dichotomy exists at the same time, although the sharp classical x, t values are linked directly with averages

Quantum Bound State

In the above case, classical results (all x points have the same weight) are obtained using a density, i.e. $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$. A different averaging process, namely $p = -i\hbar/dx \exp(ipx)/\exp(ipx)$ is used to find the sharp momentum value.. It is possible to use an average value equation, namely conservation of energy, with quantum resolution probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ to create an average entangled type of probability $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ whose $-1/2m \hbar^2/dx^2 W/W$ yields the classical $KE(x)$ value. Like in the case of $pp/2m$ in the $\exp(ipx)$ case, this should be thought of as a classical result and may be associated with sharp points in x and t . In other words, one may write: $KE(x) = .5m v_{rms}(x)v_{rms}(x)$ and use $v_{rms}(x) = dx/dt$ to solve for $x(t)$, a classical result.

How is this consistent with the $\exp(ipx)$ picture? Consider a bound quantum particle in a potential $V(x)$. One may knock out the particle from any point x with the same probability $a(p)a(p)$. If one were to create a straight classical average, one might think that:

$$KE_{ave}(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)a(p) \ pp/2m \quad ((1))$$

This, however, is a constant at each x , while $V(x)$ is not and so one cannot have a constant E at each x . This suggests that there is some kind of entanglement occurring, i.e. one does not take a straight average as in ((1)) for $KE_{ave}(x)$. In other words, the particle is not a point in x and t otherwise ((1)) should be fine. This suggests a resolution in x related to p which should be experimentally noticeable as in an n -slit experiment. Given the n -slit results, this entanglement is of a probabilistic wave structure. As a result, an average occurs, but it is an average of probabilities linked with a resolution, i.e.

$$KE_{ave}(x) = \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ pp/2m \exp(ipx) \} / \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \} \quad ((2))$$

$KE_{ave}(x)$ in this entangled form then leads to classical average notions of x and t through $v_{rms}(x) = dx/dt$.

We note that: $\langle KE \rangle + \langle V(x) \rangle = E_n$ ((3))

X in $V(x)$ is a sharp point, so we suggest that $V(x)$ must also be an average. In reality:

$$V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx) \quad ((4))$$

One may note that classical values such as x may appear in an average quantity such as $V(x)$. This may be carried further if one considers an infinite potential well. Here $V(x)$ is infinite at $x=0$ and $x=L$ and 0 inside. One has sharp x points, i.e. a classical picture, but that is fine because $V(x)$ is an average quantity. If L changes in time, one may write $L(t)$ which is again a classical average treatment.

{As a side note, one may consider two infinite potential wells with L_1 and L_2 . Eigenfunctions of the first are $\sin(n\pi x/L_1)$ for x in $(0, L_1)$ and $\sin(n\pi x/L_2)$ for x in $(0, L_2)$. In general a complete set of basis functions of one potential may be used to create a wavefunction in a section potential. Both the L_1 and L_2 eigenfunctions may be created by using weighted $\exp(ipx)$ s. We note however, that the L_1 and L_2 sets of eigenfunctions contain a boundary condition over a large range of x values i.e. the function is 0 at $x=0$ and $L=L_1$ or $L=L_2$. Thus, eigenfunctions from L_1 cannot be used to create a particular eigenfunction from L_2 . We have suggested in previous notes that a quantum bound state is one in which there is not only a bound particle, but particles tunneling in and out. The infinite well potential blocks such tunneling. A sharp x value also exists for a non-infinite well potential, but it still has a wavefunction outside the well. Thus, the idea of eigenfunctions as basis functions exists if the wavefunction may exist in all of space. For the infinite well potential, the notion of average spatial resolution still exists within the $V(x)=0$ region, but a boundary condition is imposed outside of $(0, L)$ on the wavefunction for a large range of values. }

The average of $\exp(ipx)$ s, i.e. the quantum wavefunction, still retains its link to classical averages through:

$$\langle \frac{1}{2m} \frac{dW}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} \rangle = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2W}{dx^2} \quad ((5))$$

The LHS of ((5)) is the classical average value, while overall classical kinetic energy is:

$$\text{Density} * \text{average KE} \text{ i.e. } -\frac{1}{2m} W^* \frac{d^2W}{dx^2} \quad ((6))$$

This leads to the result, when integrated over x of: $\sum_p a^*(p)a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m}$ ((7))

which shows no entanglement, i.e. interference.

Thus, the built-in classical value in the wavefunction is the result of an average of the form of ((5)) linked to curvature of W and does not consider density in space, i.e. W^*W .

In other words, the shape of the quantum crest/trough pattern defines the classical average kinetic energy, which in turn is linked with $v_{rms}(x)$ and sharp x and t values. The sharp x , t values of classical physics are linked with the spatial resolution $\exp(ipx)$ uncertainty in x through ((5)).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that there seems to exist a dichotomy in quantum mechanics. A free particle is described by $\exp(ipx)$ which suggests a resolution in x , i.e. $\hbar/p = \text{wavelength}$, which may be measured through an n -slit experiment. P , however, is a sharp value which suggests it is classical and it may be measured at each x by an impulse hit against a target. This, however, seems to be an average result, because instead of acting as a point, the particle will interfere if one uses an n -slit apparatus as the target. We suggest that p is obtained through an average procedure, i.e. $p = -i\hbar \frac{d}{dx} \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx)$. Thus, there is a link between the x -resolution picture and the sharp x - t classical one. This becomes more evident if one considers a quantum bound particle. In such a case, $\langle p^2 \rangle / 2m \text{ ave} = \{-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W\} / W = \{\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \langle p^2 \rangle / 2m \exp(ipx)\} / W(x)$ which clearly shows the average. This average KE may then be linked to $.5m v_{rms}(x)v_{rms}(x)$ which may in turn be linked to sharp x , t values. The potential $V(x)$ is also a kind of average i.e. $\text{Sum over } k \text{ } V_k \exp(ikx)$ and so may also contain average classical values. X is sharp in $V(x)$ because $V(x)$ is an average.